

Genetics

Inheritance of thermo-sensitivity for seedling color in japonica variety Fan5

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We isolated a mutant that is thermo-sensitive for seedling color in japonica variety Fan5. Expression of seedling color of Fan5 and four other japonicas was studied at temperatures of 20, 23.1, 26.1, 28, and 30.1 °C in a growth chamber. Seedling color was examined after 10 d. Thermosensitive Fan5 showed variation in seedling color at different temperatures: white at 20 °C, yellow-white at 23.1 °C, yellow-green at 26.1 °C, and green at 28 and 30.1 °C. The other four japonicas were thermoinsensitive for seedling color at all five temperatures.

Crosses of Fan5 and japonica varieties and cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) japonica line 7627 A were grown in 1991 in Hangzhou. In Oct 1992, P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, and BC₁ populations were sown in plastic pots at 20 °C.

Breeding methods

Restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines in rice

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Hybrid rice can only be developed if effective fertility restorers for CMS lines are identified and maintainers are isolated to develop new CMS lines. We evaluated F₁s of 51 hybrids, their 17 pollen parents, and 3 isogenic maintainers (B lines) of CMS lines for spikelet fertility. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications during 1991 wet

Seedling color of thermosensitive Fan5, four thermoinsensitive japonica rice varieties, and their F₁, BC₁, and F₂ populations grown at 20 °C. Hangzhou, China.

Material	Seedling color		χ^2	P
	Green	White		
<i>Parent</i>				
Fan5	0	29		
7001S	37	0		
N5047S	41	0		
Zhenong 1S	16	0		
7627 A	23	0		
<i>F₁</i>				
7001S/Fan5	15	0		
N5047S/Fan5	17	0		
Zhenong 1S/Fan5	21	0		
7627 A/Fan5 ^a	9	0		
<i>BC₁</i>				
7001S/Fan5//Fan5	52	47	χ^2 (1:1)	
N5047S/Fan5//Fan5	38	29	0.162	0.50-0.75
Zhenong 1S/Fan5//Fan5	50	56	0.955	0.25-0.50
7627 A/Fan5//Fan5	44	39	0.223	0.50-0.75
<i>F₂</i>				
7001S/Fan5	153	47	χ^2 (3:1)	
N5047S/Fan5	113	31	0.167	0.50-0.75
Zhenong 1S/Fan5	143	45	0.750	0.25-0.50
			0.638	0.75-0.90

^aF₂ from 7627 A/Fan5 was not tested due to poor seed setting in F₁.

F₁ seedlings from all crosses were green, indicating that thermosensitivity for seedling color in Fan5 is recessive (see table). The segregation ratio of green to white in BC₁ was 1:1 and in F₂, 3:1. Results showed a recessive nuclear gene controls thermosensitivity for seedling

color in Fan5. If the character can be transferred to CMS lines and their maintainers, it could be used as a morphological marker for purifying them by roguing green seedlings at lower temperature. ■

season at RRS. Each 1.7- × 0.2-m plot had a single row of 11 plants at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha and other recommended cultural practices were followed.

Spikelet fertility was assessed on five randomly selected plants in each replication for each genotype. Pollen parents were classified as effective restorers if spikelet fertility was more than 80%, as weak or partial restorers if 20-80%, as weak maintainers if 5-20%, and as effective maintainers if 0-5%.

Fourteen hybrids had more than 80% spikelet fertility, involving nine pollen parents. These pollen parents were identified as effective restorers for CMS lines V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A (see table). These prospective restorers

Maintainer and restorer lines identified for 3 CMS lines at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991 WS.

Pollen parent	Spikelet fertility ^a of hybrid with particular CMS line		
	V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
ADT36	PR	PR	R
ASD16	PR	PR	PR
ASD17	PR	PR	PR
ASD18	PR	R	R
CO 37	PR	R	PR
IR36	PR	PR	PR
IR50	PR	R	PR
IR60	PR	PR	PR
IR64	R	PR	R
IET1444	PR	PR	PR
TKM6	PR	R	R
TKM9	PR	PR	PR
TM4309	PR	R	R
TNAU801793	PR	PR	PR
TNAU88013	R	R	PR
ADT39	M	PR	PR
Jaya	PR	R	PR

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, M = maintainer.